

MILD INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY IN A SCHOOL-AGED CHILD: A CASE REPORT HIGHLIGHTING DEVELOPMENTAL, ADAPTIVE, AND EDUCATIONAL CHALLENGES

DR. DHARMENDRA KUMAR¹ | AMIT KUMAR^{2*} | DR. RAVI SHANKAR KUMAR³ | MINSHI KUMARI⁴

¹ COUNSELLOR, BUNIYAD KENDRA, SHEIKHPURA, BIHAR-811105, INDIA.

² RESEARCH SCHOLAR, DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY, MAGADH UNIVERSITY, BODH GYA, BIHAR-824231, INDIA.

³ LECTURER, DIRECTORATE OF EDUCATION, DELHI-110053, INDIA.

⁴ RESEARCH SCHOLAR, DEPARTMENT OF PSYCHOLOGY, RANCHI UNIVERSITY, RANCHI, JHARKHAND-834001, INDIA.

ABSTRACT:

Intellectual Disability (ID) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by significant limitations in intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior, with onset during the developmental period. Early identification and intervention are crucial for improving functional outcomes and quality of life. This paper presents a detailed case report of an 8-year-old boy diagnosed with Mild Intellectual Disability, who was evaluated at a child neurodevelopmental and rehabilitation center in India. The child was referred for a psychodiagnostics assessment due to concerns of delayed speech, significant learning difficulties, poor academic performance, and deficits in adaptive self-care skills. The comprehensive assessment included developmental history, clinical observation, and standardized psychological tools such as the Developmental Screening Test (DST) and Vineland Social Maturity Scale (VSMS). The results revealed a Developmental Quotient of 64 and a Social Quotient of 67.70, consistent with Mild Intellectual Disability. The child exhibited marked delays in cognitive, language, academic, and adaptive functioning, particularly in self-direction, socialization, and independent living skills. This case underscores the importance of early multidisciplinary assessment, individualized special education, speech and language interventions, and family counseling. This report contributes to the existing literature by illustrating the real-world clinical presentation and management planning for mild intellectual disability in a school-aged child within the Indian context.

KEYWORDS:

MILD INTELLECTUAL DISABILITY, DEVELOPMENTAL DELAY, ADAPTIVE BEHAVIOR, CASE REPORT, CHILD PSYCHOLOGY, SPECIAL EDUCATION.

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INTRODUCTION

Intellectual Disability (ID) is a neurodevelopmental disorder marked by significant limitations in both intellectual functioning and adaptive behavior, with onset before the age of 18 years (Tassé et al., 2016; Shree and Shukla, 2016). Intellectual functioning encompasses reasoning, problem-solving, planning, abstract thinking, judgment, academic learning, and the ability to learn from experience, while adaptive behavior refers to conceptual, social, and practical skills necessary for everyday life (Tassé et al., 2016; Shree and Shukla, 2016).

Globally, intellectual disability affects approximately 1–3% of the population, with a higher prevalence reported in low- and middle-income countries due to biological, environmental, and socio-economic factors (Baker et al., 2020). In India, childhood intellectual disability represents a significant public health and educational challenge, often compounded by delayed diagnosis, limited access to early intervention services, and a lack of parental awareness (Girimaji & Srinath, 2010).

Mild Intellectual Disability constitutes the largest proportion of individuals diagnosed with ID. Children with mild ID may not be identified until they reach school age, when academic demands increase. These children often demonstrate delays in language development, poor academic achievement, difficulties in attention and memory, and limitations in adaptive functioning, such as self-care and socialization (Dykens et al., 1990; Esteves et al., 2021; McIntyre et al., 2006; Pugliese et al., 2015). Despite these challenges, with appropriate educational support and early intervention, children with mild ID can acquire functional academic skills and achieve a reasonable level of independence in their daily lives (Crosnoe et al., 2007; De Bildt et al., 2005; Koskentausta et al., 2006; Miranda et al., 2023).

Case reports play a vital role in clinical psychology and developmental research by offering detailed insights into individual presentations, assessment processes, and intervention planning in the field. They are particularly

valuable for illustrating the heterogeneity of intellectual disabilities and highlighting culturally relevant clinical practices (Kildahl et al., 2023). The present study aims to document and analyze a detailed case of a school-aged child diagnosed with Mild Intellectual Disability, focusing on developmental history, clinical features, standardized assessment findings, and recommended management strategies. This case report seeks to contribute to the professional understanding of this condition and reinforce the importance of early, structured, and family centered interventions.

CASE DESCRIPTION

IDENTIFYING INFORMATION

The child, referred to as X for confidentiality, was an 8-year-old boy residing in a semi-rural region of Jharkhand, India. His parents brought him to a child neurodevelopmental and rehabilitation center for a psycho-diagnostic assessment. At the time of evaluation, the child was enrolled in Class I at a Hindi-medium school.

PRESENTING COMPLAINTS

The primary concerns reported by parents included the following:

- Delayed speech development
- Significant learning delay
- Difficulty with retention and recall
- Reading skills below grade level
- Writing skills below grade level
- Difficulty acquiring basic academic skills
- Dependence in dressing
- Difficulty matching shoes to the correct feet

These concerns became more pronounced after school admission, when the child was unable to cope with age-appropriate academic expectations.

INFORMANTS AND RELIABILITY

Information was obtained from both parents and children. The informants were cooperative, consistent, and reliable, providing adequate developmental and behavioral histories.

DEVELOPMENTAL AND MEDICAL HISTORY

BIRTH AND PERINATAL HISTORY

The child was born following a full-term pregnancy via a normal hospital delivery. Notably, there was a history of a delayed cry at birth, and the umbilical cord was reported to be around the neck. No subsequent reports of neonatal intensive care admission or prolonged medical complications were noted.

MEDICAL HISTORY

There was no history suggestive of:

- Severe head injury
- Epilepsy or seizure disorders

- Major physical illness
- Chronic neurological conditions

FAMILY HISTORY

The family history was non-contributory, with no reported cases of intellectual disability, major mental illness, or significant genetic disorders among the immediate family members.

DEVELOPMENTAL MILESTONES

The developmental history revealed delays across multiple domains.

Gross Motor Milestones

- Sitting: 10 months
- Standing: 12 months
- Walking: 15–16 months

SPEECH AND LANGUAGE MILESTONES

- Babbling: 9 months
- One-word speech: Present but delayed
- Two-word phrases: Present but limited

The history suggested a global developmental delay, with more prominent deficits in speech, language, and later cognitive-academic domains.

CLINICAL OBSERVATION AND BEHAVIORAL ASSESSMENT

GENERAL APPEARANCE AND BEHAVIOR

The child appeared kempt, tidy, and well-dressed. Physical appearance was age-appropriate with an average body build. Eye contact was maintained for approximately 85% of the interactions, indicating reasonable social engagement.

RAPPORT AND COOPERATION

Rapport was easily established between the participants. The child was cooperative throughout the assessment and followed the instructions with minimal prompting.

ATTENTION AND CONCENTRATION

Attention and concentration were adequate for brief tasks, although sustained attention for complex academic activities was limited.

SCHOLASTIC PERFORMANCE

The child was studying in Class I but demonstrated academic functioning significantly below expected grade level. Basic reading, writing, and numerical concepts were not adequately developed.

ASSESSMENT TOOLS AND PROCEDURE

A comprehensive psychodiagnostics evaluation was conducted using standardized instruments appropriate for developmental and adaptive assessments.

i) Developmental Screening Test (DST): The DST was administered to assess the child's overall developmental and intellectual functioning. The results indicated:

Developmental/Mental Age: 62 months

Developmental Quotient (DQ): 64

This score falls within the range indicative of a mild intellectual disability.

ii) Vineland Social Maturity Scale (VSMS): The VSMS was used to evaluate adaptive and social functioning in patients. The results were as follows:

Social Age: 65 months

Social Quotient (SQ): 67.70

Profile analysis revealed uneven development across adaptive domains, with relative strengths in basic self-help skills and greater delays in self-direction, locomotion, and socialization.

FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT

SENSORY AND MOTOR ABILITIES

- Vision and Hearing: No obvious deficits reported
- Gross Motor Skills: Walking, running, stair climbing independently
- Fine Motor Skills: Scribbling present; copying shapes and writing one word possible with verbal cues

LANGUAGE FUNCTIONING

- Receptive Language: Able to follow simple instructions, identify body parts, and recognize common objects
- Expressive Language: Limited to simple sentences

COGNITIVE AND ACADEMIC SKILLS

- Reading and writing skills were largely absent
- Number concepts and time awareness were not developed
- General knowledge and awareness of current events were minimal

SELF-CARE AND ADAPTIVE SKILLS

- Independent in toileting
- Fully dependent in dressing and matching footwear
- Limited domestic and pre-vocational skills

DIAGNOSIS

Based on:

- Developmental history
- Clinical observation
- Standardized assessment results (DST DQ = 64; VSMS SQ = 67.70)

The child was diagnosed with Mild Intellectual Disability.

DISCUSSION

This case illustrates a typical presentation of mild intellectual disability identified during the early school years. Although early motor milestones were mildly delayed, speech and cognitive deficits became more evident as environmental demands increased (Tassé et al., 2016; Shree and Shukla, 2016). The child's academic difficulties, limited adaptive independence, and language delays are consistent with the existing literature on mild ID. The uneven adaptive profile highlights the importance of assessing not only intellectual functioning but also practical life skills. The presence of basic self-help abilities alongside deficits in self-direction and socialization underscores the need for structured intervention programs (Itskovich et al., 2020; Scharf et al., 2016; Zaidman-Zait et al., 2020).

Early identification is crucial, as children with mild ID benefit significantly from targeted educational and therapeutic interventions. Without appropriate support, such children are at risk of academic failure, low self-esteem, and social exclusion (Crosnoe et al., 2007; De Bildt et al., 2005; Koskentausta et al., 2006; Miranda et al., 2023).

MANAGEMENT AND INTERVENTION PLAN

Based on the assessment findings, the following interventions were recommended:

- Special Education: Individualized, structured special education focusing on functional academics, attention, memory, and concept development.
- Speech and Language Therapy: To enhance expressive and receptive language skills, sentence formation, and communication effectiveness.
- Adaptive Skills Training: The focus is on dressing, personal care, and independent daily living skills.
- Family Counseling: To promote acceptance, understanding of the child's condition, and reinforcement of skills at home.
- Regular Follow-Up: Periodic reassessment to monitor progress and modify intervention plans is also important.

CONCLUSION

This case report highlights the multidimensional nature of mild intellectual disability and the importance of a comprehensive assessment encompassing developmental, cognitive, and adaptive domains. Early diagnosis, individualized interventions, and family involvement are critical for improving functional outcomes. The documentation of such cases contributes to clinical understanding and supports evidence-based practice in child psychology and special education.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Informed consent was obtained from the parents for the assessment and documentation. Identifying details were

anonymized to maintain confidentiality.

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